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- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“THE VEINS IN HER HAND WHO RAISED ME”

I trace the rivers over her creased skin.
Blue highways where her labor continues to linger,
Every ridge was a path with love from within
Every scar served as a bridge to support my pain

Her wrinkled fingers from years of hard gripping
held me in whispers as gentle as rain once falling
At night, they tucked me up and bandaged my scars
And swept the darkness of my grief afar

Oh, the veins that fed the roots beneath my cob,
With the hymns her heart was unable to sing, throb—
The quiet force that kept me upright and free
is still there in the valleys of the hand that raised me.

Age-drawn boundaries can become hazy over time.
But not the love that is woven into each thread.
Can never be tired or broken and faded
Forever I'll treasure your love in this heart of mine.